

Cooperativity in Spin Crossover Systems. An Atomistic Perspective on the Devil's Staircase

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Abstract

Cooperativity is key in defining the shape (i.e. gradual, abrupt or hysteretic) of thermally-driven spin transitions in magnetic switches. Despite its importance, there is very little information on its atomistic origin, which hinders the rational design of materials displaying a bistability region (i.e. hysteresis). In this paper, we investigate the spin transition of two solvatomorphs of [Fe(2-pic)₃]Cl₂, an Fe(II)-complex displaying thermal SCO from a low-spin (LS) to a high-spin (HS) state, with either gradual or abrupt two-step character. To do it, we apply a novel computational protocol to study the cooperativity of spin crossover (SCO) compounds from DFT calculations, which does not rely on *a priori* assumptions on the studied system. The distinct shape of the spin transition is successfully captured, and the atomistic origin of cooperativity is traced back to geometrical distortions of the Fe-N₆ core in case of the solvatomorph exhibiting an abrupt transition. According to our calculations, HS and LS molecules contribute differently to cooperativity, which results in a complex energetic evolution of the spin transition that cannot be described by the common Slichter-Drickamer model. The present work opens new avenues for the study of cooperativity of SCO systems having a chemically-oriented perspective, and demonstrates that quantum chemistry calculations can discriminate the shape of a spin transition, while providing insight into the atomistic underlying factors that contribute to its cooperative behavior.

1. Introduction

Recent years have witnessed a growing interest in molecular materials that may exist in two phases, with different physical properties, that can be switched ‘on’ and ‘off’ through the application of an external stimulus.¹ Within the domain of transition metal complexes, magnetism has been identified long ago as a switchable property. This is typically achieved by d^4 - d^7 metal ions such as Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} or Co^{II} when coordinated to some ligands in a pseudo-octahedral fashion, resulting in the so-called spin crossover (SCO) complexes.²⁻⁶ SCO switches

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can be triggered using temperature, pressure⁷ or light⁸⁻¹⁰ and, as such, are very promising materials for a variety of technological endeavors.¹¹⁻¹⁷ These materials are especially interesting when the 'on' and 'off' phases can coexist under identical external conditions, giving rise to *bistability*. The difference between a *switchable* and a *bistable* material is that the latter features a *hysteresis* region, which implies that the system can be either diamagnetic (*off* state) or paramagnetic (*on* state) depending on its recent history.

The key concept to understand the creation of a hysteresis region is *cooperativity*. One must have in mind that an almost-infinite number (in the order of Avogadro's constant, N_A) of magnetic configurations with variable number of HS and LS molecules exists during the spin transition. This leads to an energy-dependent HS-fraction $\gamma_{HS}(E)$ that resembles a Cantor function (also known as a Devil's staircase). The energy associated with each step of this transformation depends on both the internal changes of the molecule, and how the N_A molecules interact. The latter aspect is called *cooperativity*, and is key at defining the range of temperatures in which the full *off-on* transition is achieved. Gradual transitions are those that span over a wide range of temperatures and are typically observed in solution, where the sparse density of spin centers prevents any significant interaction between them. Abrupt transitions occurring within *ca.* 10 K are common in solids, where intermolecular interactions connect the spin centers. Finally, a hysteretic transition is achieved when cooperativity is sufficiently large to retain the system in a metastable state within a range of temperatures, thus leading to a different transition temperature for the heating and cooling modes.¹⁸ Whereas the macroscopic manifestation of cooperativity is clear, its fundamental atomistic origin is not. It is commonly attributed to the volume change that occurs around the metal ion, thus giving rise to local distortions.^{5, 19, 20} Other authors suggested that cooperativity has an important electrostatic component proportional to the charge redistribution upon SCO,^{21, 22} and that this contribution could be enhanced in case of SCO molecules attached to a metal surface thanks to the creation of mirror charges.²³ However, one must have in mind that all SCO systems present a similar volume expansion and charge redistribution upon transition, and yet display a different degree of cooperativity. It is thus clear that such structural and electrostatic changes affect each system in a different manner, and that it is necessary to evaluate the actual relevance of these two perspectives in a rigorous manner in real SCO systems.

Up to now, the theoretical analysis of cooperativity was mostly restricted to phenomenological approaches such as the Slichter and Drickamer (SD) model,^{21, 23-25} or the Ising model.^{22, 26-36} However, all these studies have in common that the model parameters are either evaluated using very simple expressions, or are obtained from the fit of experimental values thus limiting their predictive power. Only recently, the development and proper benchmark of the DFT+*U*+*D2* scheme³⁷⁻³⁹ allowed the evaluation of the model parameters using quantum chemical calculations incorporating structural and electronic degrees of freedom.^{40, 41} In these works, a methodology to study the cooperativity of SCO-systems was proposed, and the well-known complex $\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2(\text{NCS})_2$ (phen=phenanthroline) was analyzed at the LDA+*U*+*D2* and GGA+*U*+*D2* levels. Interestingly, a reasonable estimate for the phenomenological interaction parameter Γ could be obtained from first principles calculations. These investigations, however, were restricted to a unit cell of only four SCO molecules and 16 independent magnetic

configurations. Certainly, a discretization of the SCO transition using only five steps (*i.e.* from 0 to 4 HS molecules in the unit cell) seemed insufficient to represent the infinitely many intermediate steps of the SCO transition. Another shortcoming of these studies was the lack of a control experiment, *i.e.* the study of a non-cooperative SCO system. In order to improve these studies, it was necessary to find systems (i) whose transition has a different shape (for instance, abrupt *vs.* gradual), (ii) whose structure and crystal symmetry allows for a better description of their spin transition at a moderate computational cost and, finally, (iii) that are as close as possible in terms of structure and chemical constituents, which is important if we aim at identifying the microscopic origin of their distinct SCO transition shape.

Figure 1. Evolution of γ_{HS} with respect to temperature as an indication of the spin transition of **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol). The data has been extracted from ref. 42

These requisites are met in compound $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(2\text{-pic})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ (**1**, pic=picolylamine), a 50-year old SCO system first reported by Renovitch,⁴³ extensively studied later by Gütllich,⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸ and recently re-synthesized and studied by Bürgi.^{42, 49, 50} This system is particularly interesting because its phase transition depends notably on the solvent molecules present in the crystal lattice, despite of all solvatomorphs displaying a very similar crystal structure. The use of ethanol, 2-propanol, and allyl-alcohol solvates leads to two-step phase transitions at different $T_{1/2}$ (at 120, 150 and 125 K, respectively) and different degrees of cooperativity (see Fig. 1).⁴² In contrast, methanol leads to a gradual transition at *ca.* 154 K (see Fig. 1), and 1-propanol as well as tert-butyl alcohol block the HS state along the whole range of temperatures. Moreover, in the case of ethanol, an intermediate phase (IP) appears that originates in the coupling of the spin transition to an order-disorder phase transition of the solvent molecules.⁵⁰ This system became a prototype for studies of the cooperativity of SCO molecules using phenomenological models,^{28, 47, 51, 52} and led to the development of an elaborated Ising model that accounted for both the spin- and the order-disorder phase transitions.⁴⁹ Compound **1** allows us to test the performance of our protocol to describe the same SCO system presenting either a gradual or an abrupt transition under different environments. Moreover, crystals of **1** are $Z=8$, which allows us to discretize the spin transition in nine steps without the need to resort to supercells, while the small size of the system (*ca.* 450 atoms in the unit cells) keeps the computational cost under control. Such discretization is far from the actual capacity of experimental techniques,^{53, 54} but represents a significant improvement with respect to previous computational work in the field of SCO. Finally, the molecular arrangement in crystals of **1**, with charge-compensated layers of SCO molecules and counterions, separated by solvent molecules, is yet another interesting feature of **1** since it has

the potential to present a different degree of cooperativity in the inter-/intra-layer crystalline directions.

DFT calculations have been performed for the 46 symmetry-unique magnetic configurations of the unit cells of each **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol) in order to evaluate the evolution of the lattice stability along the LS-HS transition. These energies have been interpreted first using the thermodynamic SD model, retrieving cooperativity values that agree with the observation of the gradual and abrupt transitions displayed by the two aforementioned solvatomorphs of **1**. The behavior of **1**(ethanol) reveals a larger degree of cooperativity in the early steps of the phase transition upon heating (*i.e.* small γ_{HS} values), which suggested that HS and LS molecules contribute differently to cooperativity. In an attempt to explain this intriguing behavior, we have evaluated the cooperativity of the computed magnetic configurations using the concept of local structural distortions commonly employed in mathematical models. These distortions have been described using a simple descriptor, the octahedricty of the Fe-N₆ core, with different degree of success for the two solvatomorphs of **1** studied. Then, the performance of the SD model, and an improved counterpart (so-called extended SD model, xSD), in describing cooperativity is evaluated. Finally, the temperature evolution of the HS molar fraction is computed, and the results show an outstanding agreement with experiment: for both solvatomorphs the shape of the SCO transition is recovered, including the intermediate step of **1**(ethanol). Overall, this manuscript (i) presents a versatile computational approach to investigate cooperativity in SCO systems, (ii) demonstrates that quantum chemistry calculations can discriminate between a gradual and an abrupt spin transition without any experimental input beyond the crystal structure of the material, and (iii) provides insight into the atomistic underlying factors that contribute to cooperativity.

2. Methodology.

2.1. Cooperativity from DFT Calculations

In the so called mean-field approximation, the distribution of HS and LS molecules in the crystal can be summarized by the HS fraction, γ_{HS} . Under this assumption, the Gibbs energy as a function of γ_{HS} can be written as:

$$G(\gamma_{HS}) = \gamma_{HS}(\Delta H_{tot} - T\Delta S_{tot}) + \gamma_{HS}(1 - \gamma_{HS})B(\gamma_{HS}) - TS_{mix} \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_{tot} and ΔS_{tot} are the sum of the vibrational and electronic enthalpy and entropy differences between the HS and the LS states, and S_{mix} is the mixing entropy (eq. S5). The first term of eq. (1) describes effects that contribute to energy linearly with γ_{HS} . In turn, $B(\gamma_{HS})$ accounts for cooperativity of the system, and gathers any energy term that is non-linear with γ_{HS} . $B(\gamma_{HS})$ may be written, for instance, as a polynomial of degree n :

$$B(\gamma_{HS}) = \sum_{k=1}^n b_k \gamma_{HS}^{k-1} \quad (2)$$

The factor $\gamma_{HS}(1 - \gamma_{HS})$ in eq. (1) is to ensure that cooperativity vanishes for $\gamma_{HS} = 0$ and $\gamma_{HS} = 1$. The most simple polynomial of eq. (2), with $n = 1$ and $b_1 = \Gamma$, corresponds to the well known model of Slichter and Drickamer (SD model).²⁴ The advantage of the SD model (and one reason for its widespread use in the past decades) is that the effects of cooperativity can be traced back to a single parameter Γ . If Γ is zero or negative, a gradual non-cooperative transition is retrieved. A positive Γ value implies a larger energetic contribution of cooperativity at intermediate γ_{HS} . Finally, for values of Γ larger than $2RT_{1/2}$ the model predicts the opening of an hysteresis loop due to the appearance of two minima in the curve G vs. γ_{HS} .⁵⁵

It is however possible to use a higher-order polynomial, representing a more complex evolution of G vs. γ_{HS} . This case is hereafter referred to as *extended* SD or xSD model.

In the equilibrium, the variation of Gibbs energy with respect to γ_{HS} must vanish at any given temperature. By including the explicit expression of S_{mix} (eq. (S5)) to eq. (1) and deriving, one retrieves:

$$k_B T \ln \left(\frac{1 - \gamma_{HS}}{\gamma_{HS}} \right) = \Delta H_{tot} - T \Delta S_{tot} + \sum_{k=1}^n [k - (k + 1) \gamma_{HS}] b_k \gamma_{HS}^{k-1} \quad (3a)$$

In the case of the SD model, eq. (3a) simplifies to:

$$k_B T \ln \left(\frac{1 - \gamma_{HS}}{\gamma_{HS}} \right) = \Delta H_{tot} - T \Delta S_{tot} + (1 - 2\gamma_{HS}) \Gamma \quad (3b)$$

Equations (3a) and (3b) relate the thermodynamic parameters of a SCO transition to the molar fraction at each temperature. Typically, cooperativity is described with the SD model, and thus eq. (3b) is used to fit ΔH_{tot} , ΔS_{tot} and Γ from the experimentally-measured spin transition (*i.e.* γ_{HS} as a function of temperature). The goal of computational chemists is to use it in the opposite way, that is, to extract γ_{HS} from computed ΔH_{tot} , ΔS_{tot} and $B(\gamma_{HS})$ values in eq. (1). The objective of this manuscript is to get insight on the cooperativity term $B(\gamma_{HS})$.

Equation (3b) was originally conceived to describe macroscopic samples, which may be reasonably well described by γ_{HS} alone. However, DFT calculations are necessarily restricted to microscopic systems (*e.g.* unit cells) described by a *magnetic configuration* (c) that defines the individual spin state of each molecule. Whereas γ_{HS} can be univocally determined from c , the opposite is not true (for instance, $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$ belongs to 14 different symmetry-unique configurations for the compounds under study). For this reason, DFT calculations cannot evaluate Γ directly, but only a configuration-dependent Γ -term that we label as Γ_c , and define as:

$$\Gamma_c = \frac{H_{elec}(c) - \gamma_{HS}(c) \Delta H_{HL}}{\gamma_{HS}(c) [1 - \gamma_{HS}(c)]} \quad (4)$$

where H_{elec} is the energy of configuration c relative to the LS state and ΔH_{HL} is the energy difference between the all-HS and all-LS states (*i.e.* all molecules in the same spin state). This equation can be obtained starting from eq. (1) and assuming that only H_{elec} contributes to cooperativity.^{40,41} This is a good assumption considering how the remaining terms are usually evaluated computationally. Due to the size of the SCO molecules, exchange interactions between the metal spins are generally neglected and the spins are regarded as completely localized. In such case, the electronic entropy contribution (S_{elec}) is linear in γ_{HS} . With reasonable accuracy the same can be said about the vibrational contributions to entropy and enthalpy (S_{vibr} and H_{vibr}). The largest vibrational contributions are originated in the first coordination sphere of the SCO molecules and, as such, can be regarded as local vibrations.^{56,57} Only the soft vibrational modes of SCO crystals have to be described as phonons, and these modes depend much less on the spin state of the molecules. Consequently, H_{vibr} , S_{elec} and S_{vibr} are linear in γ_{HS} and, thus, their contribution to Γ_c (eq. 4) cancels out. Finally, Γ_c can be Boltzmann-weighted to obtain (i) the global cooperativity of the system Γ , or (ii) the cooperativity at each of the evaluated molar fractions, yielding $\Gamma(x)$.

2.2. A Structural Descriptor. The $\Delta CShM(c)$ values

To investigate the origin of the cooperativity, in section 3.2 we investigate the structure of the computed magnetic configurations (c) using a structural *descriptor* that aims at describing the entire unit cell in a simplified manner. Certainly, a single descriptor might not be sufficient to represent a unit cell that contains 8 SCO, 16 counterion, and 8 solvent molecules, but in view of the complexity of the subject, this simplification is a requirement for any reasonable analysis. Based on previous literature on structure:function correlations in the field of SCO,⁵⁸⁻⁶² we focused on the shape of the Fe-N₆ coordination sphere of the SCO molecules to select our descriptor. Initially, we used both the Fe-N distances and the *cis* N-Fe-N angles as in Table S1.1, but the analysis of two descriptors rapidly became too complex for our discussion in section 3.3. A much more convenient way to describe the coordination sphere is through the so-called Continuous Shape Measurements (CShM),^{63,64} which quantify the deviation of the coordination polyhedron of a mononuclear complex from the closest symmetrical polyhedron (in our case, an octahedron) as:

$$CShM_i(O_h) = \left[\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N |\vec{q}_j - \vec{p}_j|^2}{\sum_{j=1}^N |\vec{q}_j - \vec{q}_0|^2} \right] \times 100 \quad (5)$$

where \vec{q}_j and \vec{p}_j are the position vectors of the j -th atom belonging to the actual coordination sphere and the reference octahedron, respectively, and \vec{q}_0 is the geometric center of the molecule (*i.e.* the Fe atom). The denominator acts as a normalization factor that makes the $CShM_i$ values size independent.

Once we have identified our descriptor, it is now important to note that cooperativity itself, as defined in eq. (4), is proportional to the deviation of the configuration energy $H_{elec}(c)$ from the non-cooperative energy (*i.e.* $\gamma_{HS}(c) \Delta H_{HL}$). Similarly, any structural analysis must be based on the amount of deviation (or *deformation*) of the selected descriptor from a reference value, a

kind of “non-cooperative” CShM value (in analogy to a non-cooperative energy). Following this analogy, we have used as a reference the CShM of the HS (LS) molecules in the all-HS (all-LS) configuration ($CShM_{ref}^{HS/LS}$). The deviation of the CShM of each SCO molecule from the reference value yields:

$$\Delta CShM_i = CShM_i - CShM_{ref}^{HS/LS} \quad (6)$$

Notice that this approach is similar to the elasticity model proposed by Spiering *et al.*, in which cooperativity (Γ) is proportional (through the bulk modulus and Eshelby’s constant) to the ratio between the HS-LS volume difference and the average volume of an Fe-center.²⁰ Here we replace the concept of volume change by a more chemically-oriented perspective, the $\Delta CShM_i$ values. The sum of the $\Delta CShM_i$ values of all molecules in a unit cell quantifies the overall deformation of each configuration, yielding:

$$\Delta CShM(c) = \sum_{i=1}^8 \Delta CShM_i \quad (7)$$

This summation can be restricted to either HS or LS molecules in the unit cell, thus giving $\Delta CShM^{HS}(c)$ and $\Delta CShM^{LS}(c)$, respectively. This differentiation is interesting and even necessary because the energetic penalty associated to geometrical distortions of the Fe-N₆ core should be different for a LS molecule than for a HS. All this validates even more the choice of the CShM as our descriptor. First, because the deformation of the coordination sphere is likely to have the largest impact on energy and, thus, on Γ_c . Second, because it is easy to monitor the $\Delta CSM^{HS/LS}$ values based on the spin state of the molecules.

2.3. Model System, Magnetic Configurations and Computational Approach

Figure 2. (a) Representation of the unit cell of **1**(ethanol), with eight SCO molecules, sixteen counterions (Cl⁻) and eight solvent molecules (ethanol). For simplicity, H-atoms are not shown. (b) Simplified view of the SCO molecules, in which just the Fe-N₆ core is shown. The numbers indicate the order of each molecule in the strings

defining the possible magnetic configurations c (12345678, where 1-8 can be H or L). The unit cells of **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol) are isostructural, but present a translation with respect to the view offered herein.

On the Model System. All of the studied unit-cells of **1** contain eight SCO molecules in the HS state, sixteen counterions and eight solvent molecules (see Fig. 2). The SCO molecules and the counterions arrange in charge-compensated layers, which are in turn separated by the solvent molecules. For **1**(methanol), all $H_{elec}(c)$ calculations in section 3.2 have been done using the cell parameters of the X-ray structure resolved at 200 K since it is the temperature closer to the spin transition. The calculations performed for **1**(methanol), thus, assume that the unit cell parameters do not change upon transition. In turn, for **1**(ethanol), there is extensive crystallographic data, including the unit cell data just before (*i.e.* 113 K) and after (*i.e.* 125 K) the complete HS-LS transition.⁵⁰ Therefore, we have taken the X-ray structures resolved at 113 K and 125 K, to represent the “all-LS” and “all-HS” configurations, respectively, and we have interpolated them to obtain the configurations of the intermediate molar fractions (γ_{HS}). In doing so, we assume that the cell size increases (decreases) regularly with the HS (LS) molar fraction within this temperature range. In practice, the two strategies are equal, since the volume change of the unit cells of **1**(ethanol) between 113 and 125 K is actually not significant (see Supp. Info).

On the magnetic configurations (c). There are 2^8 ways to combine two possible spin states (HS and LS) in a unit cell containing eight SCO molecules ($Z=8$). Each of those distributions is what we call a magnetic configuration (c). Fortunately, symmetry rules allow us to investigate only a fraction of this number, the actual value depending on the crystal symmetry, which is P_{can} and $B_{21/c}$ for **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol), respectively. As a result, in both cases one requires 46 calculations: 1, 1, 7, 7, 14, 7, 7, 1, and 1, for molar fractions 0.0, 0.125, 0.25, 0.375, 0.5, 0.625, 0.75, 0.875, and 1, respectively. Notice that, following this approach, we have access to molar fractions being multiples of 1/8 (and between 0 and 1). Moreover, notice that we assume that the symmetry of the crystal (P_{can} and $B_{21/c}$) is maintained along the entire transition. In other words, that the intermediate molar fractions can be described using the unit cell of the all-HS ($\gamma_{HS} = 1$) and all-LS states ($\gamma_{HS} = 0$). In the present case, the crystal symmetry of **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol) was adopted experimentally considering also the intermediate step (with $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$) of the latter system. Therefore, we can be sure that, at least, the molar fractions 0, 0.5 and 1 are properly described. Concerning the other molar fractions, we assume that they are likely to be captured by any of the magnetic configurations computed. For instance, in the case of $\gamma_{HS} = 0.375$, we describe this transition step with seven possible c : HHHLLLLL, HLLHLLL, HLLLLLHL, HLHLHLLL, HLHLLHLL, HLLHHLLL and HLLHLHLL (see Fig. 2), whereas magnetic configurations with lower symmetry (*e.g.* HHHHHLLLLLLLLLLL) are not considered. One could incorporate some of the lower symmetry configurations by using supercells, at the expense of a much larger computational cost. Still, one would never reach a complete macroscopic representation of the system, so the approximation would still be present. At this stage, it is not clear to the authors whether the use of a supercell would bring any improvement to the values presented herein. In the present paper, the choice of the studied compounds, and the *model system* (above) has been done having all these elements in mind.

On the computations. In the computation of each $H_{elec}(c)$ value along the SCO transition, we optimize the structure of all molecules in the unit cell, including counterions and solvent molecules. Therefore, all molecules are allowed to modify their structure as a result of changes in their own spin state, or that of neighboring molecules. It thus follows that the internal changes of the molecule associated to the electronic structure are considered. Similarly, intermolecular interactions are also considered in our computational scheme; short-range dispersion interactions are modelled using the D2 correction, and long-range electrostatic interactions are treated at the monopole (*i.e.* atomic charges) and dipole levels. Notice that periodic-boundary conditions are applied in the three crystalline directions to simulate the studied systems at the solid-state level.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Solvent-Dependent Cooperativity. Slichter-Drickamer Model.

The cooperativity of the studied systems is analyzed by monitoring the energy of the independent magnetic configurations upon increasing molar fraction of the HS species (γ_{HS}). To do so, we have employed eq. (4), and evaluated ΔH_{HL} and ΔH_{elec} using electronic structure computations (see sections 2.3 and 5). The ΔH_{HL} values for **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol) are 8.0 and 11.3, respectively. In a non-cooperative system ($\Gamma = 0$), the enthalpy difference (ΔH_{elec}) for a unit cell with a given molar fraction would be independent from the configuration and would equal to $\gamma_{HS}\Delta H_{HL}$ (red line, Fig. 3a,c). Any deviation from this line indicates cooperativity. This can also be formulated in the following way: only energy contributions that have a non-linear dependence with γ_{HS} can contribute to cooperativity (see eq. 4).

1-Methanol. We start the analysis of the cooperativity of **1** by the gradual transition featured by **1**(methanol). One can observe an almost exact match between the actual energies of the system (black bars, Fig. 3a), and that of a hypothetical non-cooperative system (red dashed line, Fig. 3a). This is in excellent agreement with the observed gradual transition for **1**(methanol). Moreover, we notice that there is little to no spread of energies within a given γ_{HS} , which indicates that the mean-field treatment is appropriate or, in other words, that there is no *directionality* in the cooperativity. If otherwise, an Ising model could be added to account for directionality. The overall (*i.e.* Boltzmann-weighted) Γ is close to the value obtained by a fit of the experimental curve ($\Gamma_{calc} = -1.19$ vs. $\Gamma_{fit} = -0.48$ kJ/mol), both underlying the “negative” cooperativity of the system, which implies an antiferroelastic coupling (for the whole set of Γ_c values, see Section S1.1). A deeper look onto the evolution of $\Gamma(x)$ with γ_{HS} shows a rather stable value with a continuous increase of the negative cooperative behavior (see Fig. 3b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Computed H_{elec} values for the whole set of configurations of (a) **1**(methanol) and (c) **1**(ethanol), organized according to their molar fraction (black lines). In these plots, the red dashed line corresponds to the energy evolution in the absence of cooperativity (*i.e.* $\Delta H_{HL}\gamma_{HS}$). The energy of the All-LS configuration (*i.e.* LLLLLLLL) is taken as a reference. Evolution of $\Gamma(x)$ vs. γ_{HS} for (b) **1**(methanol) and (d) **1**(ethanol)

2-Ethanol. For this system, the degree of cooperativity is clearly larger than the case of **1**(methanol). The overall Γ is 6.0 kJ/mol, far larger and of different sign than that of **1**(methanol) (for the whole set of Γ_c values, see Section S1.2). The evolution of $\Gamma(x)$ with γ_{HS} shows (i) a peak at low molar fractions ($\Gamma(1/8) = 18.2$ kJ/mol), (ii) a plateau at intermediate configurations, and (iii) a final decrease as the SCO transition evolves. This behavior is rather interesting because it describes a cooperativity value Γ that changes significantly with respect to γ_{HS} . Such evolution is in contrast to the SD model, which assumes a constant Γ , whose contribution to G is largest at $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$ and decreases symmetrically for values above and below (eq. (1)). These results indicate that the dominant contributions to Γ depend on the ratio of HS and LS molecules, and predominate in the early steps of the LS-to-HS transformation. Indeed, the peak of $\Gamma(\gamma_{HS})$ at small molar fractions is very interesting by itself; it also leads to a peak in the evolution of the free energy along γ_{HS} (see Fig. 3c and Section S1.2), which works as a sort of activation barrier, and implies that a cooperative SCO transition is delayed up to higher temperatures with respect to the non-cooperative analog. Finally, we notice that the overall value of Γ is larger than $2RT_{1/2}$ (6.0 vs. 2.0 kJ/mol) and, accordingly, indicates an abrupt-and-possibly-hysteretic transition in the SD model (see section 2.1).

Concerning the two-step transition experimentally observed for **1**(ethanol), it has been reported that its origin is an order-disorder process that affects the ethanol molecules of the lattice (see Fig. 1).⁵⁰ The whole process is described as a “re-entrant” transition in which the unit-cells of the LT and HT phases are equivalent ($P2_1/c$ space group) whereas that of the intermediate phase (IP) is doubled ($B2_1/c$ space group).⁵⁰ To simplify the comparison between the three phases, the $B2_1/c$ space group was finally adopted for all of them in the original experimental paper. In our calculations, the structure of this IP is only partially reproduced. Whereas the distribution of SCO molecules in the IP is taken into account by the configurations with $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$ that we have computed, we do not observe the two disordered structures for the solvent molecules. In

all our calculations, the solvent molecules display the “gauche” structure and there is no evidence of any other conformation. Still, as we will show and discuss in section 3.3 our calculations are able to capture the plateau corresponding to the IP, which suggests that its appearance is not necessarily related to the order-disorder process of the solvent molecules.

3.2. Microscopic Insight into the Origin of Cooperativity

To investigate the microscopic origin of the cooperativity, in this section we try to connect the Γ_c values computed in the previous section, with the structure of the optimized unit cells. To rationalize the complex crystal structure of the studied systems, we employ a descriptor derived from the CShM values of each Fe center. A discussion on the requisites of the descriptor and its mathematical treatment is offered in section 2.2. The key point is that our descriptor is, indeed, the amount of deviation of the CShM values from a reference “non-cooperative” CShM value (in analogy to the non-cooperative energy in eq. (4)). This value is labelled as $\Delta CShM(c)$, and is defined in eq. (6). In turn, the contribution to $\Delta CShM(c)$ corresponding to the HS and LS molecules is defined as $\Delta CShM^{HS}(c)$ and $\Delta CShM^{LS}(c)$, respectively. In Table 1 we collect the $\Delta CShM(c)$, $\Delta CShM^{HS}(c)$, and $\Delta CShM^{LS}(c)$ values for the configurations of **1**(ethanol) associated with smallest and largest values of Γ_c for each set of γ_{HS} . Additionally, for $\gamma_{HS}=3/8$, we show the results for the entire set of configurations. For an interested reader, the $CShM_i$ values of each Fe center in the studied configurations can be found in section S3 in the ESI.

Table 1. Relationship between structural distortions of the SCO molecules in selected configurations (c) of **1**(ethanol) (see Fig. 2 for labeling) and the associated Γ_c . The structural distortion is evaluated using the CShM of all 8 molecules present in the unit cell (see section 2.2). Only shown the c with largest (max) and smallest (min) cooperativity at each molar fraction except for $\gamma_{HS} = 3/8$, in which case we show all c .

γ_{HS}	c		Γ_c	$\Delta CShM^{LS}(c)$	$\Delta CShM^{HS}(c)$	$\Delta CShM(c)$
1/8	HLLLLLLL		18.24	0.128	0.037	0.165
2/8	HLLLHLLL	max	9.93	0.158	0.176	0.334
	HLLLLLLH	min	8.09	0.106	0.105	0.211
3/8	HHLLHLLL	max	6.75	0.166	0.194	0.360
	HLHLHLLL		6.20	0.159	0.194	0.353
	HHLLLLHL		5.65	0.111	0.141	0.252
	HLLHHLLL		5.51	0.088	0.193	0.281
	HHHLLLLL		5.31	0.081	0.103	0.184
	HLLHLHLL		4.93	0.096	0.174	0.270
	HLHLLHLL	min	4.39	0.100	0.284	0.384
4/8	HHLLHHLL	max	5.66	0.205	0.339	0.544
	HLHLLHLH	min	1.90	0.056	0.590	0.646
5/8	HHHLHLHL	max	4.37	0.131	0.355	0.486
	HHHLLHLH	min	2.13	0.031	0.361	0.392
6/8	HHHLHLHH	max	4.27	0.112	0.240	0.352
	HHHHLLH	min	2.14	0.080	0.254	0.334
7/8	HHHHHHHL		-0.66	0.015	0.455	0.470

Within each molar fraction, it can be seen that larger overall distortions (*i.e.* $\Delta CShM$) are generally associated with larger cooperativity values (compare *max* and *min* entries in Table 1). The relation becomes even clearer when we focus on the deformation of the LS molecules (*i.e.* $\Delta CShM^{LS}$). Comparing $\Delta CShM$ values of different γ_{HS} sets requires some additional treatment. The reason is that according to the definition of Γ_c in eq. (4), the same energy

difference (*i.e.* numerator in eq. (4)) leads to a different Γ_c depending on γ_{HS} . To allow comparison, a measure of energy distortion independent of γ_{HS} is needed. Consequently, in Fig. 4 we plot the numerator of eq. (4) against $\Delta CShM^{HS}$ (red points) and $\Delta CShM^{LS}$ (black points). In this way, it is possible to identify a correlation between cooperativity and the degree of distortion of the LS and HS molecules.

Cooperativity is larger when the structural distortion is concentrated in LS molecules and decreases when it is absorbed by HS Fe-centers, even if the latter present a larger degree of structural distortion. This explains the asymmetric behavior of Γ_c with respect to γ_{HS} as observed in Fig. 3d. The quality of the correlation is significant, considering that we used a simple descriptor (*i.e.* the $CShM$) and that other effects are likely to contribute to cooperativity beyond such structural distortion. A linear fit yields R^2 values of *ca.* 0.59 and 0.56 for LS and HS molecules (dashed lines in Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Relationship between structural distortion, evaluated using the ΔCSM of HS (red points) and LS molecules (black points), and energetic deviation from a non-cooperative case, evaluated using the numerator of eq. (4) for (a) **1(ethanol)** and (b) **1(methanol)**. Dashed lines correspond to the best linear fits.

The relevance of the structural distortion of the Fe-N₆ core to cooperativity is further evaluated by comparison with the case of **1(methanol)**, which displays a non-cooperative behavior. In section S4 of the ESI we collect the $CShM_i$, $\Delta CShM^{HS}$, and $\Delta CShM^{LS}$ values for **1(methanol)**. These data shows that: (i) the $CShM_i$ values are systematically smaller for both HS and LS Fe-centers (compare Tables S3.1 and S3.2a), which indicates that the molecules are less distorted in **1(methanol)** crystals independently of the spin configuration, most likely due to the smaller size of the solvent. Also, that (ii) both $\Delta CShM^{LS}$ and $\Delta CShM^{HS}$ are smaller in the case of **1(methanol)** with respect to those of **1(ethanol)** (*ca.* 33% in average). This indicates that the successive spin transition of Fe centers has a smaller structural impact on their neighbors. In this case, however, there is no correlation between energetic and structural distortions as we observed for **1(ethanol)** (linear fit yield R^2 values of 0.2 and 0.0 for LS and HS molecules, respectively).

Overall, the analysis performed in this section demonstrates that the degree of distortion of the Fe-N₆ core, quantified using the $CShM$ values, is a major contributor to the cooperativity of **1(ethanol)**. Similar levels of distortion, however, do not lead to cooperativity in the case of **1(methanol)**. This might indicate that such distortion is only relevant in systems that display some cooperativity (*e.g.* **1(ethanol)**) and not in systems displaying a gradual transition (*e.g.* **1(methanol)**). One could generalize this statement by saying that the cooperative ($\Gamma > 0$), non-

cooperative ($\Gamma \cong 0$) and anti-cooperative regimes ($\Gamma < 0$) might have different dominant sources. Alternatively, we might conclude that such structural analyses are completely system- and solvatomorph- dependent, preventing any rationalization of cooperativity based on simple structural descriptors of wide applicability. To answer this question, more studies need to be performed.

3.3. Simulation of the γ_{HS} vs. T curves from Computational Data.

The results obtained from the DFT calculations have been rationalized so far using the SD model (section 3.1) and by looking at internal molecular distortions (section 3.2). In this section, we try to interpret the information contained in the set of DFT energies as a whole. Our aim is first to identify, for the two solvatomorphs studied, the best phenomenological model to describe the cooperativity of the two systems, and later apply it to simulate the γ_{HS} vs. T curves of the two studied solvatomorphs. In the case of **1**(methanol), the non-cooperative (*nc*) model (*i.e.* $\Gamma = 0$ in eq. (1)) is sufficient to fit with good quality the calculated electronic energies (see σ in Table 2). Using the SD model (eq. (1)), we get a very small negative Γ (-0.6 kJ/mol), and the quality of the fit is roughly the same (see Table 2 and Fig. 5). This is in line with the observation that **1**(methanol) undergoes a non-cooperative spin transition.

Table 2. Parameters obtained from fitting the DFT energies using the nc, SD and xSD models (given in kJ/mol). The quality of the fit is quantified using the average and maximum deviations between energy values obtained from these models and from DFT calculations.

	ΔH_{tot}	Γ (SD) or $b_1 - b_5$ (xSD)	Std. dev. (σ)	Max. dev.
1 (methanol)				
nc	7.6	-	0.13	0.45
SD	7.8	-0.6	0.12	0.40
1 (ethanol)				
nc	12.9	-	0.73	1.8
SD	10.2	8.9	0.54	1.2
xSD	11.1	26.8, -99.8, 141.8, -60.6, -6.4	0.18	0.5

In the case of **1**(ethanol), the *nc* model leads to a poor description of the spin states ($\sigma = 0.73$ kJ/mol). The incorporation of cooperativity through the SD model yields a large positive Γ (8.9 kJ/mol) but still poor agreement with the computed values ($\sigma = 0.54$ kJ/mol). A reasonable agreement ($\sigma = 0.18$ kJ/mol) is only achieved by the xSD in which the polynomial expansion is brought to 5th order (*i.e.* using eq. (2) with $n = 5$). Within this model, the energy necessary to flip a molecule from the LS to the HS state is largest in the realm of small HS fractions (up to $\gamma_{HS} \approx 0.125$) and then decreases with increasing HS fractions (see Fig. 5). This is the manifestation of what is already observed in Figure 3d and discussed in section 3.3; an asymmetrical behaviour of Γ with respect to γ_{HS} . Interestingly, a change of slope appears at $\gamma_{HS} \approx 0.5$, and later at $\gamma_{HS} \approx 0.7$. In between, a region appears in which B is almost constant.

Figure 5. Energy contribution of cooperativity, (*i.e.* the second term in eq. 1) as a function of the HS fraction for **1**(methanol) (blue line, SD model) and for **1**(ethanol) (red line: SD model, green line: xSD model). All parameters are given in Table 2.

At this stage, we proceed to simulate the γ_{HS} vs. T curves using the *nc*, SD and xSD models (see Fig. 6). To do so, eq. (3a) has been solved iteratively using temperature-dependent computed values of ΔH_{vib} , ΔS_{vib} and a constant value of $\Delta S_{elec} = 13.38$ J/K·mol (see section S4 for details), whereas ΔH_{elec} is chosen to match the experimental transition temperature. The reason is that the computational prediction of $T_{1/2}$ is still not sufficiently accurate. Adopting a computational estimate of ΔH_{elec} would mostly shift $T_{1/2}$ of the associated transitions (see also Section 5). For **1**(methanol), both the *nc* model and the SD model predict the gradual shape of the transition with similar quality, with $\Delta H_{elec} = 19.5$ kJ/mol.

Figure 6. Experimental (black) and computed (red) γ_{HS} vs. T curves for **1**(methanol) (left) and **1**(ethanol) (right).

For **1**(ethanol), the *nc* model does not qualitatively reproduce the SCO transition (as expected). In turn, the SD model with $\Delta H_{elec} = 18$ kJ/mol, and both the Γ computed in section 3.1 (6.0 kJ/mol) and the one fitted in this section (8.9 kJ/mol), predict a too-abrupt transition and the opening of an hysteresis loop, which suggests an overestimation of Γ . Indeed, this was expected given the inability of the SD model to describe the complex energetic contribution of cooperativity in Figure 5. Moreover, this model cannot describe the step observed experimentally at around $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$. In turn, the xSD model using the b_1 - b_5 parameters obtained from the DFT energies (see Table 2), and a fit ΔH_{elec} value of 21.0 kJ/mol, is able to capture both the abruptness of the transition, and the intermediate step (see Fig. 6 and Section S4). Concerning the first point, it is likely that the cooperativity of the early steps of the transition is overestimated, since the gradual tails at the beginning of the transition disappear in our calculated curves. However, the appearance of the intermediate step is extremely remarkable, since it is obtained using a mean field model for the first time, and deserves some comments. Its width changes with the value of ΔH_{elec} used in the fit, but is rather robust, in the sense that it does always appear for values of ΔH_{elec} leading to a transition at around the experimental $T_{1/2}$ (see Fig. S2a). Also, it only appears when computing the curve in the *cooling* mode (*i.e.* starting from the evaluation of γ_{HS} at 400 K and decreasing temperature) and not in

the *heating* mode (*i.e.* from 5 K and increasing T), in which case the transition is shifted towards very high temperatures (see Fig. S2b). This is due to the difficulty of overcoming the activation barrier at $\gamma_{HS} = 0.125$ starting from $\gamma_{HS} = 0$, which again suggests that the cooperativity in the early steps of the transition might be overestimated. When the system is set artificially after the barrier when solving the curves, the transition obtained in *cooling* mode is recovered (see Fig S2b). Finally, the origin of this step is found in the almost-flat region at around $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$ in the evolution of the cooperativity term with respect to γ_{HS} as depicted in Figure 5. It is worth stressing that this evolution stems from the DFT energies computed in section 3.2 without any *a priori* assumption on the characteristics of **1**.

An important aspect of the xSD model, is that the resulting $T_{1/2}$ is shifted depending on the b_1 - b_5 parameters. In principle, this is at odds with the common understanding of cooperativity, which is based on the SD model. In this model, a modification of Γ does not lead to a change in $T_{1/2}$ (*i.e.* last term of eq. (3b) cancels out at $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$). As a result, one can assume that cooperativity only changes the shape of the transition, but not the temperature at which it occurs (*i.e.* $T_{1/2}$). On the contrary, with the xSD model, there are non-zero energy contributions at $\gamma_{HS} = 0.5$ (see eq. (3a) and eq. (S6)) that result in $T_{1/2}$ being shifted depending on the b_1 - b_5 parameters. This is how the model captures potential peaks of $\Gamma(\gamma_{HS})$, as observed in Figure 3d, and has important implications: it shows that $T_{1/2}$ cannot be predicted only from ΔH_{tot} and ΔS_{tot} , as is common in computational works, for systems displaying a cooperative behavior that requires a more-complex expression than the SD model.

4. Conclusions

We present a computational protocol to study the cooperativity in SCO systems. It consists on (i) the calculation of the energy of successive steps of the LS-HS transition using DFT (section 3.1), (ii) the fit of these energies to a mathematical model, such as the SD or the xSD model, describing the cooperativity term (section 3.3) and, finally (iii) the computation of the γ_{HS} vs. T curves using the best mathematical model. This protocol is able to capture the degree of cooperativity displayed by the two solvatomorphs **1**(methanol) and **1**(ethanol) exhibiting a gradual and an abrupt two-step transition, respectively. We find this achievement of significant interest to the realm of materials design, since it demonstrates that quantum chemistry calculations can discriminate the shape of a phase transition with the minimum structural input. Moreover, the DFT calculations provide a wealth of structural data from which an atomistic interpretation to cooperativity can be extracted (section 3.2).

In the case of **1**(ethanol), we observed that the degree of cooperativity is larger in the early steps of the LS-to-HS transformation and decreases along with the increase of HS molar fraction γ_{HS} , which suggests that LS and HS molecules contribute differently to cooperativity. This point has been analyzed by evaluating the relationship between cooperativity and structural distortion, the latter quantified using the degree of octahedrlicity of the Fe centers as a descriptor (CShM values). We observed a clear correlation between the two terms, and a distinct behaviour of the LS and HS centers, which explains the aforementioned decrease of cooperativity along γ_{HS} . Such complex γ_{HS} -dependence of the cooperativity cannot be captured by the classical SD

model. Instead, we required an extended SD model (xSD) in which the description of cooperativity is done using a polynomial of 5th order (in contrast to the SD model that is restricted to a single parameter, Γ). The xSD model is able to properly describe the energetics of the SCO transition for this solvatomorph, and successfully reproduces its two-step abrupt transition.

Overall, the present work opens new avenues for the study of cooperativity in SCO transitions having a chemically-oriented perspective. Evidently, the study of a SCO material displaying hysteresis and/or directionality are in our priorities. Also, the impact of some approximations needs to be tested, especially the number of steps in which we can discretize the LS-HS transition. At this stage, we believe that this is the bottleneck of our computational protocol, and is most likely the reason for the observed overestimation of cooperativity in the early steps of the transition of **1**(ethanol). Finally, we want to note that the DFT computations describing the SCO transition of the different solvatomorphs of **1** represent a wealth of data that requires further analyses, with the aim at identifying further (or better) structural descriptors describing the microscopic origin of cooperativity.

Concerning the implication of our results on **1**(ethanol), we recall that the cooperativity of this compound has been extensively studied in the past, and that the latest interpretation ascribed the appearance of the intermediate step to an order-disorder process that affects the ethanol molecules of the lattice.⁵⁰ As we discussed in section 3.2, in all our calculations the solvent molecules display the “gauche” structure, which means that this conformation is always the most stable in terms of enthalpy. Therefore, our calculations strongly suggest that the order-disorder process associated with the solvent molecules is triggered by entropy, which would also explain the different occupation probabilities of the two disordered positions at different temperature.⁵⁰ The computational modelling of order-disorder processes require molecular dynamics simulations,^{65, 66} which is out of the scope of this work. However, our DFT calculations, even if they do not capture the order-disorder process of ethanol, are able to describe the two-step transition of **1**(ethanol). This indicates that the appearance of the intermediate step might not be due to the order-disorder process of the solvent molecules.

5. Computational Details

All energy evaluations have been performed using the Quantum Espresso package (QE) Version 5.2. using the PBE+ U +D2 scheme, which implies a U parameter of 2.65 eV on the “ d ” orbitals of iron, and the D2 correction of Grimme.⁶⁷ We have used the spin unrestricted formalism, Vanderbilt pseudopotentials⁶⁸ and a Γ -point sampling of the Brillouin zone. In section 3.1, the computation of H_{elec} for all configurations has been done by means of fixed-cell optimizations, in which the cell parameters remain constant, and a kinetic energy cutoff of 35 Ry. Approximately one hundred fixed-cell geometry optimizations have been performed during this project, with a consumption of approximately three-hundred thousand CPU hours. The spin state of each iron atom in the unit cell is set by defining an appropriate initial guess (LS or HS) that is maintained along the optimization.

The method employed herein (*i.e.* PBE+ U +D2) has a mean absolute error of 4.4 kJ/mol when describing the H_{elec} of Fe-N₆-based SCO systems,³⁹ which may translate into an error of 50-100 K in $T_{1/2}$. For this reason, ΔH_{elec} has been fit in section 3.3, to simulate the γ_{HS} vs. T curves. An improved parametrization of U specifically for **1** could lead to a reduced error in H_{elec} and, thus, in $T_{1/2}$. To this purpose, the Hubbard U should be determined *a priori*, to correct H_{elec} and to absorb the errors associated with the prediction of ΔH_{vib} , ΔS_{vib} and ΔS_{elec} . However, the error associated with the U parameter adopted in this paper is likely to depend linearly with γ_{HS} and, therefore, to cancel out in the computation of Γ_c as in eq. (4). In other words, the degree of cooperativity is probably not influenced by the choice of U , whose effect is limited to the prediction of $T_{1/2}$.

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Supporting Information

Supporting Information Available, including (i) the Complete Set of Computed Energies and Γ_c values, (ii) Details on the Evaluation of the Free Energy, (iii) the Complete Set of CShM Values, and (iv) Details on the Simulation of the γ_{HS} vs. T curves.

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Table of Contents:

The atomistic origin of cooperativity is investigated for an Fe(II)-based SCO compound that presents either a two-step abrupt or a gradual transition depending on the lattice-solvent molecules, using a novel computational approach based on DFT calculations